

Homologous series of azomesogens : 4-(4'-n-Alkoxybenzoyloxy)-phenyl azobenzenes

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A homologous series of twelve homologues have been synthesized containing carboxy (-COO-) and azo (-N=N-) central groups. First to seventh homologues of the series are enantiotropic nematic and tenth to sixteenth homologues exhibit polymorphism enantiotropically. The behaviour of the series and its mesophase thermal stabilities are compared with other structurally related series.

Mesogenic compounds generally consists of long, narrow and fairly rigid molecules with or without terminal and lateral substituents. Terminal and lateral groups present in the molecule have their own importance in exhibiting liquid crystalline behaviour. The present newly synthesized homologous series does not have any terminal or lateral substituent other than -H which is a part of the aromatic core.

Results and discussion

4-Hydroxy phenyl azobenzene is non-mesomorphic in nature. However, the mesomorphic characteristic is induced by linking it with alkoxy benzoic acids through carboxylate unit as one of the central groups. The transition temperatures of the series are shown in Table 1. All the mem-

bers of the series display mesomorphism in an enantiotropic manner except the eighth member of the series in which smectic mesophase appeared monotropically. Methyl to heptyl homologues are enantiotropic nematic and decyl to hexadecyl homologues are poly mesomorphic with the exhibition of smectic and nematic type mesomorphism enantiotropically. The plot of transition temperatures versus the number of carbon atoms in n-alkyl chain (Fig. 1) follows a zig-zag path of rising and falling nature upto the fifth homologue and shows overall falling tendency beyond the sixth homologue with negligible rise at the seventh and

Table 1. Transition temperatures for 4-(4'-n-alkoxy benzoyloxy) phenyl azobenzene

No. of carbon atoms in n-alkyl chain	Transition temperature in °C		
	Smectic	Nematic	Isotropic
1	-	138.0	154.0
2	-	148.0	186.0
3	-	116.0	145.0
4	-	124.0	156.0
5	-	110.0	136.0
6	-	115.0	135.0
7	-	112.0	129.0
8	(100.0)	106.0	128.0
10	103.0	108.0	124.5
12	91.0	112.0	122.0
14	91.0	115.0	122.0
16	101.0	121.0	125.0

Value in parentheses indicate monotropy.

Fig. 1. 4-(4'-n-Alkoxy benzoyloxy)phenyl azobenzenes : (●) solid mesomorphic, (x) smectic isotropic or nematic smectic (-) nematic isotropic.

tenth homologues. The nematic-isotropic transition curve shows a smooth falling tendency as the series is ascended. The alternation in transition temperatures for even and odd number of carbon atoms is clearly observed which indicates different terminal end-end interactions because the shorter alkoxy chain is extended strictly along an axis determined by tetrahedral bond angles. The interaction diminishes as the series is ascended.

Table 2 shows average thermal stabilities and stage of commencement of smectic phase for the homologous series which are structurally similar and selected for comparative study.

Series	I	A	B
Smectic-isotropic or Smectic-nematic	114.0 (C ₁₀ -C ₁₆)	192 (C ₁₂ -C ₁₆)	148.7 (C ₆ -C ₁₆)
Commencement of smectic phase	C ₁₀	C ₁₂	C ₆
Nematic-isotropic or Isotropic-nematic	146 (C ₁ -C ₈)	260.3 (C ₁ -C ₁₀)	213.6 (C ₁ -C ₁₀)
Commencement of nematic phase	C ₁	C ₁	C ₁

The molecular geometry of all the homologous series under comparison consist of three phenyl rings linked through -COO- and -N=N- central linkages with left n-alkoxy group. The right end terminal groups are -H, -COCH₃ and -Cl for series I, A and B respectively.

Series :

Fig. 2. Homologous series for comparison¹.

The variation in mesomorphic characteristics can be attributed to the presence of different right terminal groups which reveal liquid crystal behaviour latent in the parent system.

The nematic thermal stabilities of series A and B are

higher than that of series I. This is understandable as the terminal groups -COCH₃ and -Cl enhances overall polarity and polarizability of the molecules, whereas series I has no terminal substituent. The molecules displaying nematic property are capable of resisting the strong thermal vibrations maintaining the parallel orientations of the molecules by terminal attractions in the floating condition.

The commencement of smectic phase depend upon the extent of non-coplanarity caused by a molecule. The extent of non-coplanarity caused by -COCH₃ is more than -H and -Cl terminals. Thus the degree of variation in coplanarity affects the formation of a layered structure which gives rise to smectic phase. The smectic phase commences from tenth member of series I, from twelfth member of series A and from sixth member of series B.

The order of commencement of smectic phase as suggested by the title series can be presented as follows in terms of terminal substituents at the other end : -Cl > -H > -COCH₃.

The study suggests the following group efficiency order on the basis of thermal stability : smectic : -COCH₃ > -Cl > -H; nematic : -COCH₃ > -Cl > -H.

Experimental

4-Hydroxy phenyl azobenzene², 4-n-alkoxy benzoic acids and their acid chlorides were synthesized according to literature method³. 4-(4'-n-Alkoxy benzoyloxy) phenyl azobenzene were synthesized by condensing the azo dye in pyridine and the products were crystallized from alcohol. The transition temperatures were observed through a Leitz Laboulux 12 POL polarizing microscope with heating stage. Analytical data confirmed the structures.

IR spectra : 4-(4'-n-propyloxy benzoyloxy)phenyl azobenzene : 686, 762 cm⁻¹ (mono sub. benzene ring), 846 cm⁻¹ (para sub. benzene ring), 1068 cm⁻¹ (C=O bend), 1164 cm⁻¹ [(C-O str. (ester)], 1261 cm⁻¹ [(C-C str. (alkyl chain)], 1475 cm⁻¹, 1508 cm⁻¹, 1603 cm⁻¹ (aromatic -C=C- str.) 176 cm⁻¹ (C=O), 2878, 2938, 2931 cm⁻¹ (sat. C-H str. alkyl).

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